

IMPACTS OF MODERNIZATION ON TRADITIONAL MARRIAGE CEREMONY OF THE IBIBIO ETHNIC GROUP OF SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative research used ethnographic methodology to investigate impact of modernization on Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony, among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Modernization theory was adopted for a theoretical framework. Fetterman big-net approach was adopted by the researcher for randomly selection of participants from Etinan, Ibesikpo-Asutan, Ikono and Uruan local government areas. Method of data collection include interview, participant observation and key informant interview. Instrument for data collection was interview guide which was used by the researchers. Data were analysed thematically with excerpts from responses of the study participants. Findings of the study through gathered data show that the order of events during traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio has changed due to influence of modernization. Changes were observed in traditional attires, order of traditional rites and introduction of strange delicacies. Among others, the researcher recommended that the Ibibio people should endeavour to promote their cultural values in order to preserve the existence of the fourth largest ethnic group in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Traditional marriage, culture, Ibibio and traditional rites

INTRODUCTION

Culture is universal and marriage is a culture trait. Marriage is an important cultural practice that characterizes every cultural group. Every ethnic group across the earth defines its cultural pre-requisites and processes through which marriage contract is performed, marriage is engaged and the processes or conditions through which marriages are disengaged. These

cultural pre-requisites, processes and conditions form the cultural patterns of marriage for a given cultural or ethnic group, and they are culturally defined by the people which make them differ from one cultural group to the other. These cultural definitions of the cultural groups form the traditions for which the people uphold, preserve their marital practices, and transfer same as traditions from one generation to the other. Traditional African Marriage is a complex institution, involving several stages and characterized by the performance of constituted rites (Ndu-Udeji, 2021).

Marriage from the beginning was meant for the procreation and promotion of life (Kyalo, 2022). Marriage and the idea of marriage are universal but with its definition, there is no one generally acceptable definition of marriage due to its cultural contexts (Ogoma, 2014). Marriage is a relationship between one or more men (male or female) and one or more women (female or male) recognized by society as having a continuing claim to the right of sexual access to one another (Haviland, 2000). Marriage is a transaction and resulting contract in which a woman and a man are recognized by society as having a continuing claim to the right of sexual access to one another, and in which the woman involved is eligible to bear children (Haviland 1996).

Marriage is a union between a man and a woman such that the children born to the woman are recognized as legitimate offspring of both partners. According to Edmund Leach cited in Haviland (1996), marriage can, but doesn't always, accomplish the following: establish the legal father of a woman's children and the legal mother of a man, give either or both spouses a monopoly in the sexuality of the other, give either or both spouses rights to the labour of the other, give either or both spouses rights over the other's property, establish a joint fund or property which is a partnership, for the benefit of the children and establish a socially significant relationship of affinity between spouses and their relatives.

Modernization is an encompassing process of massive social changes that, once set in motion, tends to penetrate all domains of life, from economic activities, social life, to political institutions, in a self-reinforcing process (Inglehart and Welzel, 2005). Modernization brings an intense awareness of change and innovation, linked with the idea that human societies are progressing (Inglehart and Welzel, 2005). Capitalist notions of modernization have consciously or unconsciously adopted the Marxist idea that modernization starts with changes at the socioeconomic basis, from which it moves on to changes in the institutional and cultural superstructure. The term modernization connotes first of all changes in production technology inducing major economic transitions from preindustrial to industrial societies and from industrial to post-industrial societies. The post-industrial societies are characterized by high level of technological innovations which have brought about the ease path of globalization with influence of culture battles which have produce the dynamic nature of culture through culture shift (Inglehart and Welzel, 2005).

Marriage is a complex of social, political, religious, and economic systems in Ibibio which covers diverse aspects of the society as family and community relationships, sex and sexuality, inheritance, and even political power (as rulership particularly in the past resided in specific and designated families both the secular and the religious) (Ubong, 2010). Marriage in Ibibio land is believed to perform many functions which include procreation, regulate sexual behavior, fulfill economic needs of partners, perpetuates kinships group, and provide institution for enculturation or socialization of children. These functions have over the ages

made marriage a valuable institution among the Ibibio people of the Southern Nigeria. Most social relations are constructed on the basis of marriage union (Wilson, 2007).

The technology which drives modernization has brought about the influences of different cultures of the various parts of the world to Africa and with the high level of illiteracy in Africa, the exploit of technology upon culture and cultural values is fast becoming a great challenge to the African traditional values and the resulting societal problems. The advancement in technology and its consequent globalised influence through various forms of information communication technology has brought changes to the world with many African nations pushing for development thereby buying into the technological phase through internet and satellite television, and the use of handheld phones which bring the various cultures of the world into the hand of the majority of Africans like in Nigeria.

The Ibibio people of Southern Nigeria has been part of the Africans who are making influential use of handheld phone and other forms of technology like the internet and satellite television. Ubong (2010) has posited that what has changed significantly in marriage in Ibibio land has to do with performance during traditional marriage ceremonies, ending the function at night, alterations arising from conflict during negotiations on required traditional items on the 'list' to size of bride price. It is observable that technology has enhance diverse forms of influential shifts in the dynamics of the Ibibio culture especially in the area of traditional marriage ceremony. The shift has brought about different forms of conflicts from the immediate family system to the external societal influence. It is clearly witnessed today within the Ibibio society, that traditional forms of Ibibio marriage and its functions are facing challenges due to culture shift forced by the influence of modernization through the high rate of use of technology among the people. This is creating serious socio-cultural issues among families and the society. According to Paul and Peters (2023), most marriages experience economic, emotional and spiritual instability and hardship which are often the characteristics of post-marriage ceremonies, which are as results of recent changes in Ibibio traditional marriage. Some girls are growing older without suitors, some grooms to-be have decided to practice co-habitation instead of going out for full marriage, girls are becoming single parents in their parents houses and young people are reluctant of going out for full traditional marriage, thereby making the Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony a function for some people. Against this backdrop, having identified the gap in influence of modernization on the traditional marriage system among the Ibibio people of Southern Nigeria, this research sought to examine influence of modernization on the traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State in South-South region of Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Concept of Marriage

Marriage from history until recent has been a sacred relationship between man and woman. Odejobi (2013) described marriage as a social institution that unites people in a special form of mutual dependence for the purpose of finding and maintaining a family. It is a culturally sanctioned union between two or more people that establish certain rights and obligations between them, their children and their in-laws. Marriage is an important and natural process in human life that has existed in all cultures and periods in different forms. It has attempted to bridge two ideas with different values and ideologies and to construct human relations.

Havillard et al (2011) noted that when viewed within the entire range of the past and present societies, marriage is more or less a durable union sanctioned by society. However, it is necessary that the relationship be formed and conducted in accordance with written customs and taboos as in primitive societies or in accordance with the established laws as in more sophisticated societies. (Encyclopaedia Americana, 1988 cited in Odunayo and Oyewole, (2019).

Marriage according to Haviland (2000) cited in University of Houston (2023), is a relationship between one or more men (male or female) and one or more women (female or male) recognized by society as having a continuing claim to the right of sexual access to one another. Marriage is a transaction and resulting contract in which a woman and a man are recognized by society as having a continuing claim to the right of sexual access to one another, and in which the woman involved is eligible to bear children (Haviland 1996 cited in University of Houston, 2023). Marriage is a union between a man and a woman such that the children born to the woman are recognized as legitimate offspring of both partners (University of Houston, 2023).

According to Ogoma (2014), marriage is an essentially contentious concept. Marriage and the idea of marriage are universal and there is no one generally acceptable definition of marriage, which makes the definition of marriage relative. Ogoma (2014) further gave various definitions of marriage derived from encyclopaedia as a socially or ritually recognized union or legal contract between spouses that establishes rights and obligations between them and their children, and between them and their in-laws. The import of this definition is that where there are no children, there is no marriage. The same authority as reported by Ogoma traces the origin of marriage to the Middle English, marriage which was also a derivative of Old French *marier* which means to marry. *Marier* is also derived from a Latin word *maritare*, meaning, to be provided with a wife or husband. The same authority goes ahead to cite other authorities, among whom are; Edvard Westermarck who defines marriage as: “a more or less durable connection between male and female lasting beyond the mere act of propagation till the birth of the offspring.” Westermarck was to reject the definition years later and gave another more controversial definition of marriage as: “relation of one of one or more men to one or more women that is recognized by custom or law.” Ogoma (2014) also quotes from the anthropological handbook: Notes and Queries, that marriage is: “a union between a man and a woman such that children born from the woman are the recognized legitimate offspring of both partners.” None of these definitions meet our curiosity but they have been cited just to show how controversial the concept can be.

Marriage is an important and natural process in human life that has existed in all cultures and periods in different forms (Zaheri *et al*, 2020). It has attempted to bridge two ideas with different values and ideologies and to construct human relations. In addition, marriage aims to fulfill a variety of basic human needs such as generation survival and upbringing the children, fulfilling the dream of being parents, achieving the highest level of friendship and intimacy, labor division, cooperation, assisting one another in married life, having a safe place for peace and flourishing skills, as well as achieving human perfection and elevation and mental health (Zaheri *et al*., 2019).

Ayisi (1997) cited in Ogoma (2014) defines marriage as the process whereby a man and a woman come together to form a union for the purpose of procreation. However, marriage can

be seen as an intended temporary or permanent union between a man and a woman that is socially, culturally or legally recognized (Ogoma, 2014). In other words, marriage is not just an agreement between a man and a woman to live together without the knowledge of others of the kind of relationship that exists between them. Marriage is a public matter. Tonizek (2008) identifies three different types of marriage which are; traditional, court and white marriages. White marriage is done in the Churches and Mosques where clergies preside over the affairs. The Court marriage is done under the law of the state. The traditional marriage is the local form of marriage. However, it is common to see some people taking part in all these forms of marriage.

Marriage from the point of institution of art is a drama in which everyone becomes an actor or actress and not just a spectator. Marriage is regarded as a complex of social, political, religious, and economic systems in Ibibio land (Udo, 1983 cited in Ubong, 2010). According to Ubong (2010) marriage covers diverse aspects of the society as family and community relationships, sex and sexuality, inheritance, and even political power (as rulership particularly in the past resided in specific and designated families both the secular and the religious). The family is not just a component of the man, the wife and their children, but the departed souls, relatives and the unborn generations are regarded as members of the family which make marriage not the union, or the joining of a man and a woman for the purpose of becoming husband and wife (Ubong, 2010).

According to Nmah (2012), for marriage to be marriage, there must be a will or two wills meeting together, that is, there is the consent between the man and the woman which is known as the matrimonial mutual will. According to Shorter (2001), marriage takes many cultural forms, but a general definition of marriage can be given. Marriage according to Shorter is an intimate union between a man and a woman, of which mating is an essential and sacred expression, establishing enforceable rights between them, marking a change of status for them and their parents, giving the children of the union a higher status than extramarital ones, generating relationships of consanguinity and affinity, implying that other forms of mating or intimacy are deviant or preparatory to marriage (Igodo, 2020).

African Conception on Marriage and Family

Marriage is as important as life in Africa. Marriage occupies an important position in the affairs of Africans, and without marriage, there is no family, and without a family, one could not bear children (Ogoma, 2014). The connection between marriage and family can hardly be separated among the traditional Africans. According to Ayisi (1997) as cited by Ogoma (2014), the family is then the logical outcome of marriage. A family consists of a man, his wife, and child or children. By this definition, Ogoma (2014) posits that a childless marriage is not a family and an individual belongs to at least one family in his lifetime. Since the family is the basic unit of any political and social organizations, the process of erecting it should and was given serious attention among the traditional African societies. Marriage, for Africans, though it is purposely for procreation, is more than that. Marriage serves other purposes. According to Ogoma (2014), for African peoples, marriage is the focus of existence. It is the point where all the members of a given community meet: the departed, the living and those yet unborn. All the dimensions of time meet here and the whole drama of history is repeated, renewed and revitalized.

African traditional conception of marriage is teleological. It is primarily for procreation. Marriage can be dissolved on the ground of childlessness. The importance attached to children is however without basis. One major reason for that attachment is summed up in what call is 'personal immortality.' To the African people, whenever a man dies, it is imperative for his offspring to bear his name, so that his name and lineage does not die. According to Awolalu and Adelumo (1979) cited by Ogoma (2014), the Yoruba attach importance to child-bearing. Unfruitful marriage is not only a misfortune but also a curse since the couple have not contributed to the community of the family and therefore, of the society.

In an agrarian society, especially in the past, the manliness of a man was measured by his farm produce. The higher the produce, the greater the respect accorded a man. Many hands in the farm led to greater output. Also, leadership roles and chieftaincy titles were reserved for men who had many wives and children under them. The reasoning behind this is that, a man who could control many wives and children, if given leadership roles, would be effective. Africans were not taught how not to die, but they believed that if they have many children, some of them would outlive them even if some of them would die (Ogoma, 2014).

The Concept of Traditional Marriage

Traditional marriage customs place great importance on parental consent and family involvement in the choice of couple's marriage partner (Odunayo and Oyewole, 2019). In Africa, traditional marriage plays great role in ascertaining the legality of marriage among the people though the custom is culturally relative. This could have accounted for the relatively fewer divorces in the past because elders could be assumed to see through their noses more clearly than the young people that would have been blindfolded by what they call love (Odunayo and Oyewole, 2019). Traditional marriage in African context used to have many rites of passages like the virginity test which was one of the factors that checkmate pre-marital sex and infidelity but today, traditional virginity test which helps to check indecency and pre-marital sexual relationships seem to have been abandoned (Odunayo and Oyewole, 2019).

Traditional Africans in general, and the Yoruba in particular, laid much premium on marriage because they know that if the foundation is weak, the entire building (that is, the society) will be negatively affected. They know that nothing can be built on nothing. They know that individuals make up the family and families make up the community. To build a strong and stable society therefore, the family must be well-founded (Ogoma, 2014).

Anthropologically, traditional marriage is the primary established form of marriage recognized in a given country or religious or social group at a given time: In that culture, traditional marriage requires the families of the future bride and grooms to engage in ritual visits and exchange gifts. Traditional marriage ceremony in many parts of Africa depends on payment of a bride price and in the past, the tradition of bride price was believed to have operated to give formal recognition to marriages and protect wives against abuse, stabilize the partnership and to join the two families together (Paul and Peters, 2023).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Modernization theory

Modernization theory is used to explain the process of modernization within societies. The "classical" theories of modernization of the 1950s and 1960s drew on sociological

analyses of Karl Marx, Emile Durkheim and a partial reading of Max Weber and were strongly influenced by the writings of Harvard sociologist Talcott Parsons. Modernization refers to a model of a progressive transition from a "pre-modern" or "traditional" to a "modern" society. Modernization theory suggests that traditional societies will develop as they adopt more modern practices. Proponents of modernization theory claim that modern states are wealthier and more powerful and that their citizens are freer to enjoy a higher standard of living. The theory looks at the internal factors of a country while assuming that with assistance, "traditional" countries can be brought to development in the same manner more developed countries have been. Modernization theory both attempts to identify the social variables that contribute to social progress and development of societies and seeks to explain the process of social evolution. Authors such as Daniel Lerner explicitly equated modernization with Westernization.

Modernization has greatly influenced the quest for change especially through western education in most of the traditional or rural societies across the world. The desire to be aligned with the developments of the western countries and other parts of the nation, the Ibibio people have chosen to adopt other dressing patterns from other culture to replace the dignified Ibibio traditional wears during traditional marriage ceremonies. In recent times, Ibibio young men are feeling ashamed to tie wrappers and some of them do not know how to tie the wrapper and are so uncomfortable with it. The quest to look-like and behave-like the civilized of the modern culture have made our young ones to push the Ibibio cultural patterns and practice in traditional marriage ceremonies to extinction.

METHODOLOGY

Ethnographic research design was adopted by the researchers for the study. This research design involves multiple qualitative data collection techniques such as in-depth interview, key informant interview, focus group discussion and objective observation by the researchers. The study was conducted in four Ibibio local government areas across Akwa Ibom State. Etinan Local Government Area, Ibessikpo-Asutan Local Government Area, Ikono Local Government Area and Uruan Local Government Area were selected for the study. Two villages were randomly selected from each of the four selected local government areas.

The researcher through Fetterman (2010) big-net approach randomly selected participants from one village per local government area. Study participants were randomly selected who co-operated, and were ready to give answers to the questions as were required. Method of data collection include interview, participant observation and key informant interview. Instrument for data collection was interview guide which was used by the researcher and his three research assistants. Data were analysed thematically with excerpts from responses of the study participants.

RESULT

Changes in Traditional Attires during Traditional Marriage Ceremony

Emergence from findings of the study shows that modernization in term of fashion through the many means of internet reach has greatly influence the mode of dressing among the Ibibio people. This influence has brought about a great shift in the dressing of the Ibibio

people who were known among the people of the Niger region of Nigeria to dress with wrappers, shirts or blouses with traditional hats as relatively connected to the ethnic culture of the group within the South-South region. Findings have revealed that, there is a culture shift in the mode of dressing especially during traditional marriage ceremonies of some Ibibio people.

The majority of the study participants agreed through their responses to interviews that there have been situations whereby an Ibibio man or woman will rather prefer another cultural attire to the Ibibio traditional wrapper and shirt or blouse during their traditional marriage ceremony. One of the study participants during interview reported that;

My brother we are seeing different things these days with our children. May be it is because they are fortunate to travel out or may be it is because of the big phones they use today which according to them they can reach anywhere through their phones. They are borrowing so many things into our traditional marriage ceremony which were not part of our traditional marriage ceremony. Like today as I observed along stadium road, I saw a picture of the traditional marriage and I thought it was a Yoruba boy who was coming to marry our daughter because of the Yoruba *apada* that he wore. But when I find out, it was our son in the Yoruba attire. What is wrong with our own wrapper or our cultural wears? Are we now saying that their traditional wears are better than our own? We have to curtail this influence else, we will be strangers in our own land (male, 63 years, Etinan, Retired Civil Servant)

Another participant from Uruan Local Government Area in his responses reported that;

There is a lot of changes in our dressing code during marriage ceremony here in Uruan. Before now, we used to wear what is called *Ayoioyo* which to alot of people, it is believed to be the Efik traditional dress. The *Ayoioyo* is Uruan traditional dress for women especially in traditional occasions or ceremonies like the traditional marriage ceremony. But today there have been several changes in terms of our mode of dressing in Uruan. The young generation are copying everything they see in television and phones and so many of them do not know about their culture which is the more reason why they are wearing everything they see and everything they feel is attractive to them. These changes have to be control. We have to begin to promote our traditional wears especially during occasions like the traditional marriage (Male, 60 years, Uruan, Trader)

Data gathered through interview revealed that there exist shift in culture of the Ibibio people and this is very visible in the dressing patterns of the people during some traditional marriage ceremony across the Ibibio land. The majority of the study participants agreed that most of the Ibibio sons and daughters have decided to showcase traditional attires of other culture instead of promoting their cultural attires. Some factors were found to be responsible for the shift in the traditional dressing during some traditional marriages among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State.

Changes in the Traditional Order of Traditional Marriage Ceremony

Findings through data collection show that there are lots of changes in the traditional marriage ceremony patterns among the Ibibio people in these modern days as compare to what was obtainable in the past. Traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people according to data gathered by the researcher had specified patterns which have over the years been shifted as result or impact of modernization. Findings of the study revealed that there are lots of changes in the patterns of Ibibio's traditional marriage ceremony. One of the study participants from Ikono Local Government Area in her responses reported that;

You see today we are all victims of modernity which has brought about changes within the life patterns of the Ibibio people and as a reflection of such, is the changes in the patterns of traditional marriage ceremony. In our own days, traditional marriage use to take place in the late evening through the night. Let say around 6 to 7 pm, the groom family will arrived for *udia ibeye* which was cooked in the evening after the bride's mother might have come back from the market with her siblings and relatives to prepare the meals for the groom's family which the size were manageable as compare today which we call crowd to witness traditional marriage ceremony instead of family members who will take the young girl home and nurture her as their wife. But what we have today is much more cooking and outrageous expenditure because we want crowd to come, in fact today people feel more satisfy based on the large crowd that turn up in their traditional marriage ceremony. This is a change that has happen among us the Ibibio people (Female, 61 years, Ikono, Trader)

Another study participant from Uruan Local Government Area in his responses reported that;

Traditional marriage ceremony used to be between the two families and strangers we were not concern with strangers as we are today. Family members especially the elderly used to go and get their daughter in-law for their son. Mind you, the groom's father was not part of the ceremony. All that the groom's father does was to send item to the proposed daughter in-law's family. The groom's father used to send an elder of the major family (Ekpuk) to represent him. The elder will go with some other elders and selected elderly women who are members of the groom's family for the ceremony which was mostly indoor activity. On return, the bride's family will send cook food and raw food items like yam, fish or goat for the groom's father and other members of the groom's member who were not part of the ceremony.

He further narrated that:

The elder who represented the groom's father in the company of the other elders and women will take the new bride the groom's father with the groom and handed over the couple to the groom's father as a sign of successful mission delivery. On the reception of the bride, the groom's father will call his wife who is the groom's mother if alive; call his other

daughter in-laws if any and call other wives of his brothers and neighbour and they will share the food the elders brought from the ceremony which was given by the bride's family. The groom's father will introduce each woman to the new bride as a wife of the family after she was first introduced. The man will also ask the old wives to assist the new bride were necessary, he will tell the old wives that if they see her come to cut leaves at their backyard they should allow her and if she needs salt, and they should give it to her as one of them and said same to her. This was how marriage was done in those days. But today, there are so many things I see today which I believe that it is the new world that has influence our people and most importantly, our people do not know our culture and traditions anymore and nobody cares to learn from the elders, they are doing what they see others do and they copy them (Male, 71 years, Idu, Uruan).

Traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio peoples experienced culture shift. Gathered data from participants revealed great dimensions of changes in the cultural practice of traditional marriage. It was gathered that what was obtainable before as part of the Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony are missing today and new cultural elements have been introduced into the practice.

Strange delicacies and drinks and Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony

Findings from gathered data show that there have been changes in quantity and types of foods presented during Ibibio traditional marriage ceremonies today as compare to what was obtainable in the traditional Ibibio society. In the case of quantity, finding show that in the traditional Ibibio society, foods were prepared for few members of the groom's family and for the father of the groom who will not accompany the team to the ceremony but wait at home for his daughter in-law. One of the study participants from Etinan Local Government Area in his responses reported that said that:

My brother what we see today is not what used to be before. In our days and in the days of my father, foods were very few kinds. What we have as “Udia Ibege” today was made for few people because traditional marriage ceremony used to be for very few elders of the groom's family. We used to have soups like *afang*, *editan*, *atamam* and most especially *ubó* which were made of vegetable leaves and cocoyam's leaves. We also used to have *itimehe akpapa* and roast corns picked from the bride mother's *ubium*. But today, we have some people cook different kinds of foods which are not part of our culture. Mind you that rice was not an important food as we make it be today. Some people even engage caterers to cook and these caterers have brought various strange foods into our culture and we are gradually losing our traditional foods. It is a pity that some of our children do not know these foods and how to cook them and in the nearest future I will not be surprise if indomie noodles in part of the Udia ibege of my people. But before, I know I will die and rest with my fathers (Male, 72 years,

Etinan, family head).

During Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony, emergence of findings shows that the foods were few and the cost was affordable base on the quantity which was relative to the expected visitors. One of the study participants from Ibesikpo Asutan Local Government Area in her narrative reported that:

When I was given to my husband, my mother was not under any pressure and my father was happy because he was going to host visitors he can afford. He called my mother, gave her some money and my mother added her own and we went to the market on the market day to buy food items for my husband's family. It was not something that my parent had to go looking for where to borrow money for food or what is called entertainment today. Most of the leaves and vegetables were gotten from my parent's farm because we were not expecting to cook for 50 people. But today, our people have to cook other tribe's foods during our traditional marriage because in some cases the groom may not come from here unlike before that we used to marry among ourselves. Because the bride's family and the expected couples are faced with large number of visitors and sometime groom coming from another tribe, they have to cook strange foods to satisfy the groom and his family. Because of the large expected turn up of visitors, the families involve are now battling on the cost of cooking these food and drinks, and what type of food should be cooked. Our traditional marriage ceremony is no long what it used to be (Female, 65 years, Ibesikpo, trader).

Further findings from collected data revealed that due to the introduction of new or what the study participants referred to as strange foods, the bride's family have now shifted the burden of entertaining their visitors which was the culture of the Ibibio to entertain their visitors, to the visitors paying for or sponsoring their entertainment at the proposed bride's house. Findings also revealed that the issue of entertainment money was not there before now. But today groom's families are asked to pay for entertainment because of the expected visitors and family members. One of the study participants from Uruan Local Government Area in his narratives reported that”

It is our tradition as Ibibio to entertain or visitors, but this has changed due to changes in the traditional marriage practice of the Ibibio people today. The introduction of strange foods and drinks into our traditional marriage ceremony has brought about so many changes. I believed that it is the high cost of entertaining the high numbers of visitors that has brought about the shift of entertaining your visitors to the visitors entertaining themselves. Many kinds of foods are seen today at traditional marriage ceremonies especially were the people engaged the services of caterers. These caterers are destroying our culture with their strange foods which they claim are better to our health that what we have as our traditional foods. Imagine, how someone can say that

fried rice is richer than “Itemehe Akpakpa”. Well it is the new world that is influencing everything in Africa, (Male, 69 years, Uruan, Businessman).

Traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people has been experiencing changes in the terms of ceremonial foods. Gathered data show that the majority of the study participants' referred to the new set of foods as strange foods. This implies that a lot of foods served today at Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony are strange to the traditional foods known and cultivated by the Ibibio people.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study through gathered data show that the order of events during traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio has changed due to influence of modernization which is made possible through the dynamic nature of culture. One of the visible changes as discovered through gathered data is the changes in the traditional attires of the Ibibio people during their traditional marriage ceremony. It is discovered that a lot of Ibibio sons today are not wearing their traditional wrapper and chieftaincy gown during traditional marriage ceremony. Data show that the wear other ethnic group's traditional attires for Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony. This is as a result of influence of components of modernization like the internet and mobility. The finding give credence to Inglehart and Welzei (2005) who posit that modernization brings an intense awareness of change and innovation.

Other emergence of findings is the changes in the traditional order of activities during Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony. Data show that the traditional marriage ceremony that used to take place in the late evening is now billed to start in the afternoon. Also, the bride's family that used to wait to sit and host their visitors and now brought out with songs and dance. This and other changes have made the patterns culture shifts which are experienced among the Ibibio people during their traditional marriage ceremony. This is also in agreement with the postulation of Inglehart and Welzei (2005) who posit that modernization brings an intense awareness of change and innovation.

Further emergence is the fact that in the Ibibio traditional marriage, the entertainment that was mainly the bride's family is now shifted to the groom and his family. It was discovered that what is called “*Udia Ibeje*” or entertainment is now the groom's responsibility depending on the number of expected visitors from the groom's side and the bride' side. This shift has affected cost and kinds of foods found among the traditional marriage ceremonies of the Ibibio people. This changes has given credence to Inglehart and Welzei (2005) who posit that modernization brings an intense awareness of change and innovation.

CONCLUSION

Traditional marriage among the Ibibio people of Southern Nigeria is a very important event which authenticates marriage as a traditional institution as obtainable in other parts of Africa. There have been observable changes in the traditional marriage ceremonies of the Ibibio people. Some of these changes are in adoption of other ethnic group's traditional attires by Ibibio sons during their traditional marriage ceremonies, changes in the patterns of activities during the traditional marriage, and introduction of strange foods which have brought about the

shift in bearing the entertainment (*udia ibeye*) cost from the bride's family to the groom.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Ibibio people should promote Ibibio traditional attires in order to encourage the upcoming generations of using examine traditional attires especially during traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, South – South Nigeria
2. The elders of the Ibibio ethnic group should project appropriate order of traditional rites for the traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, South – South Nigeria
3. Delicacies of the Ibibio people should be uphold by the people in order to avoid extinction in the nearest future.
4. The Ibibio people should endeavor to promote their cultural values in order to preserve the existence of the fourth largest ethnic group in Nigeria.

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